

REPOPSI End-Project Evaluation Using the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model

Source

FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines (1.0). <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

About the Repository

REPOPSI (www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/) is an open repository for psychological measures, scales, tests, and other research instruments in Serbian. It is maintained by researchers at the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences ([LIRA](#)) at the University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy. REPOPSI instruments are deposited in an Open Science Framework (OSF) project at osf.io/5zb8p/.

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This report was created as part of the project titled "TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs", which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017536. The project has received support from the [EOSC Future](#) through the [RDA Open Call mechanism](#), based on evaluations of external, independent experts.

Evaluation Method

Measuring progress (for more details see *6.1 Measuring progress*, p. 34).

While “it is likely that FAIR practices can vary a lot from one community to another, eventually because their requirements can be different” (*3.4 Evaluation methods*, p. 10), we chose not to discard any of the indicators.

Evaluation by Indicator

F - Findable

F1 (F1-01M, F1-01D, F1-02M, F1-02D) - Metadata and data are identified by a persistent and globally unique identifier

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: For every metadata record and digital object that it describes (data) a globally unique identifier (GUID) is assigned. OSF is listed in the FAIRsharing registry service at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.g4z879>. For every metadata record there is a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), minted by DataCite.

Read more on GUIDs on the OSF Support page, [Project and Components FAQ's](#), *What's a globally unique identifier (GUID)? What metadata is maintained about them?* question.

F2-01M - Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Description metadata is provided by OSF, which implements the DataCite Metadata Schema (source: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.g4z879>). Additionally, every digital object (i.e. psychological instrument) is enriched with embedded metadata that further describes its provenance, citation, contributors, and provides instructions on how to use the digital resource.

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F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier for the data

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Data identifiers are included in machine-readable XML documents that are deposited with every digital object (i.e. psychological instrument) on the OSF and that are in compliance with the latest version of the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) (Version 4.4). These XML metadata documents are generated based on the tabular REPOPSI_inventory CSV ([osf.io/mxrc2/](#)) file on the OSF. Metadata with data identifiers are also listed in a tabular REPOPSI_inventory XLSX ([osf.io/2j7y8/](#)) file on the OSF as well as in a [Google spreadsheet](#) that users can browse using an [interactive web app](#).

Accessing all public data from metadata is possible via OSF’s open API (documentation is available at <https://developer.osf.io/>; an example of data retrieval from API is available at <https://api.osf.io/v2/nodes/f9mpd/files/osfstorage/>).

F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: All public metadata is easily accessed through the OSF API. Metadata are indexed in the Datacite, Crossref, Google Scholar, SHARE, Europe PMC, and Web of Science indexes (source: [How OSF Meets ‘Desirable Characteristics for Data Repositories’](#)).

A - Accessible

A1-01M - Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Metadata contains all information to enable the user to access the data. The Repository follows an easily navigable scheme and access to data is straightforward.

A1-02M - Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Visitors to the Repository can access metadata through the user interface. All REPOPSI metadata is publicly available.

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A1-02D - Data can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Visitors to the Repository can access all the available data through the user interface. There is a user guide available on the REPOPSI Wiki page (osf.io/5zb8p/wiki/home/) and on the REPOPSI website (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/repopsi-guide/>).

A1-03M - Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: All metadata records are enriched with a DOI that resolves to a metadata record.

A1-03D - Data identifier resolves to a digital object

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: All data objects are enriched with a GUID that is unique and permanent and that resolves to a designated digital object.

A1-04M - Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Repository metadata can be accessed through standardised protocols like HTTP. OSF also provides every necessary documentation on how to use the API for accessing the metadata.

A1-04M - Data is accessible through standardised protocol

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Data can be accessed through the standardised HTTP protocol.

A1-05D - Data can be accessed automatically (i.e. by a computer program)

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Data can be accessed through the OSF open API. OSF provides all necessary documentation on how to use the API at <https://developer.osf.io/>.

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A1.1-01M - Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Repository metadata can be accessed through the standardised HTTP protocol. This protocol is freely available and extensively used.

A1.1-01D - Data is accessible through a free access protocol

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Repository data can be accessed through the standardised HTTP protocol. This protocol is the standard protocol for data exchange on the Internet and is freely available.

A1.2-01D - Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: OSF supports authentication and authorisation. Specifically, it is possible to make OSF components private (source: [Control Your Privacy \(OSF Projects\) Settings](#)) and grant access to them on a user-to-user basis (source: [Grant Access to a Project \(OSF Projects\)](#)) At the moment, however, REPOPSI does not use this service since all data (psychological instruments) are open and available under a Creative Commons licence.

A2-01M - Metadata is guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: OSF has a partnership with Internet Archive for long-term preservation with a \$250k preservation fund (source: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.q4z879>). If a data file is deleted or withdrawn, the GUID will always resolve to a page that provides metadata about the removed file (file name, storage provider, if the deletion occurred on OSF or on an add-on service, name/GUID of user who deleted the file, and timestamp of file deletion). For deleted or withdrawn projects, components, and users a similar page will exist at that GUID noting that the content has been removed (source: [Project and Components FAQ's](#), *What's a globally unique identifier (GUID)? What metadata is maintained about them?* question).

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I - Interoperable

I1-01M - Metadata uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format

METRIC - "2" - under consideration or in planning phase

Explanation: XML metadata documents that are deposited with every digital object (i.e. psychological instrument) on the OSF are in compliance with the latest version of the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) (Version 4.4) and are, therefore, machine actionable and usable. However, metadata is still not in a standardised knowledge representation format. Putting metadata in the Resource Description Framework (RDF) or similar formats is currently being considered.

Out of the OSF metadata fields, only the timestamp is not given in a form of free text and is generated automatically following the ISO 8601 standard.

I1-01D - Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: All files describing instruments are in PDF and ODT formats, which are very much in use within the target community (i.e. psychology researchers and students).

I1-02M - Metadata uses machine-understandable knowledge representation

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Every metadata record has a permalink in the form of a DOI. These DOIs are minted by DataCite (source: [Project and Components FAQ's](#), *I have a project on OSF but searching the associated DOI on google doesn't bring up the page in results. Is the DOI active?* question), which automatically transforms metadata in a machine-understandable knowledge representation form like JSON-LD and Schema.org.

I1-02D - Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation

METRIC - "1" - not being considered yet

Explanation: Machine-understandable knowledge representation of data files is not being considered at the moment. Although all files in the Repository are in ODT format, which is part of an OpenDocument Format and based on an open standard (OpenOffice XML file specification), we do not believe that this can be seen as a form of a standardised knowledge representation.

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I2-01M - Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: REPOPSI metadata uses the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH). LCSH is used to express subject classifications, although currently with only one term (“[Psychological tests](#)”). LCSH has a machine-readable structure and is documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers. It is listed in the FAIRsharing.org registry as an example of a controlled vocabulary that conforms to the FAIR principles (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.d31795>).

I2-01D - Data uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies

METRIC - “1” - not being considered yet

Explanation: Using controlled vocabularies for data is not under consideration at the moment.

I3-01M - Metadata includes references to other metadata

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: XML metadata documents that are deposited with every digital object (i.e. psychological instrument) on the OSF are in compliance with the latest version of the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) (Version 4.4). These metadata documents contain references to other metadata through links to information about, for example, journal articles and preprints, OSF projects/components or websites that are related to the digital object that the metadata describes.

I3-01D - Data includes references to other data

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Currently, most of the data objects include references to other data in the form of a DOI pointing to a journal article or preprint, while some of the data objects also include a GUID pointing to where the authors additionally stored the psychological instrument on OSF, outside of REPOPSI.

I3-02M - Metadata includes references to other data

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: XML metadata documents that are deposited with every digital object (i.e. psychological instrument) on the OSF are in compliance with the latest version of the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) (Version 4.4). These metadata documents are connected to other data by

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linking to, for example, related journal articles or preprints that provide additional context to the data.

I3-02D - Data includes qualified references to other data

METRIC - "1" - not being considered yet

Explanation: This is not under consideration at the moment.

I3-03M - Metadata includes qualified references to other metadata

METRIC - "1" - not being considered yet

Explanation: This is not under consideration at the moment.

I3-03D - Metadata includes qualified references to other data

METRIC - "1" - not being considered yet

Explanation: This is not under consideration at the moment.

R - Reusable

R1-01M - Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Both metadata and data provide enough information to allow everybody to use it without any difficulties or ambiguities. Information about the versions of records is provided as well.

R1.1-01M - Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be reused

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Every metadata record includes the information on the licence and terms of use. It is available in both human-readable and machine-understandable form.

R1.1-02M - Metadata refers to a standard reuse licence

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Every metadata record includes the information on the licence and terms of use. Metadata refers to a Creative Commons licence.

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R1.1-03M - Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: All data is licensed under a Creative Commons BY-NC-SA licence. Since OSF does not provide an option to choose this kind of licence, this information is embedded in the XML metadata documents that are deposited with every digital object (i.e. psychological instrument) on the OSF. These documents are in compliance with the latest version of the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) (Version 4.4) and the licence information is provided in the “Rights” metadata field.

R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: All metadata have provenance information that is in accordance with the community-specific standards in the field of psychology (e.g., the scientific article where the original instrument or the instrument translation was first published, the names of the people who translated the instrument).

R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: All metadata have provenance information that is in accordance with the community-specific standards in the field of psychology (see under R1.2-01M). However, this language is straightforward and can be easily understood by academics from other fields (especially social sciences and humanities).

R1.3-01M - Metadata complies with a community standard

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: OSF implements DataCite Metadata Schema which is a generalised metadata schema (source: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.q4z879>). Furthermore, each data file is enriched with embedded metadata that complies with the community-specific standards in the field of psychology.

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R1.3-01D - Data complies with a community standard

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: All the data are in PDF and ODT formats, both well-known and well-used in the target community (i.e. psychology researchers and students).

R1.3-02M - Metadata is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Metadata is expressed with DataCite Metadata Schema (source: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.g4z879>), which has a machine-understandable standard that can be used in the target community.

R1.3-02D - Data is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Data is in PDF and ODT formats. PDF is a de-facto standard in many communities when it comes to textual documents. ODT is part of an OpenDocument Format and based on an open standard (OpenOffice XML file specification), which means that it is represented in a machine-understandable way.

Conclusion

This report is the result of a self-assessment test at the end of the project titled “TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs” (project team members: Aleksandra Lazić, Ljiljana Lazarević, Danka Purić, Iris Žeželj, Obrad Vučkovic). We have previously used this test at the beginning of the project to get a better idea on where to concentrate efforts to make REPOPSI resources more FAIR; the report of that self-assessment test, from December 2022, is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535023>. Comparing the start- and end-project tests, we can evaluate the progress we made.

Figure 1 visualises the results of the current evaluation of the indicators for all the FAIR areas. It was created using the spreadsheet provided by the FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group, available at <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>.

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Figure 1 FAIR Maturity Visualisation for REPOPSI

Note. Numbers refer to the five levels of compliance: 0 – not applicable; 1 – not being considered yet; 2 – under consideration or in planning phase; 3 – in implementation phase; 4 – fully implemented.

All of the indicators for Accessibility were already fully satisfied at the start of the project, so there are no changes when it comes to this principle. Notable improvements have been, however, made to assure greater adherence to the principles of Findability, Interoperability, and Reusability. These principles have been enhanced by putting the REPOPSI metadata values into a machine-readable format and by implementing a FAIR-compliant controlled vocabulary ([Library of Congress Subject Headings](#)). We developed a Python code to generate XML metadata documents in compliance with the latest version of the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) (Version 4.4) and deposited these documents with every digital object (i.e. psychological instrument) on the OSF. Further details about this project activity are available in the report titled

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“Piloting the Application of a Controlled Vocabulary to an OSF-Hosted Repository: The Case of REPOPSI” at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8178798>.

At the start of the project, REPOPSI did not adhere to only one of the Findability and the Reusability indicators. Thanks to the described metadata enhancements, it now satisfies them fully. Specifically, the F3-01M (*Metadata includes the identifier for the data*) and R1.1-03M (*Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence*) principle have changed from being “under consideration or in planning phase” to being “fully implemented”. We overcame the limitations of the OSF platform by including all data GUIDs and a machine-understandable reuse licence in the XML metadata documents in the OSF components of every deposited psychological instrument.

The maturity levels were, at the start of the project, lowest for the Interoperability principle. Because we have since structured the REPOPSI metadata according to the latest version of the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) (Version 4.4) and applied a FAIR-compliant controlled vocabulary ([Library of Congress Subject Headings](#)), the following three Interoperability indicators, which were previously marked as “not being considered yet” are now “fully implemented”:

- I2-01M - *Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies*
- I3-01M - *Metadata includes references to other metadata*
- I3-02M - *Metadata includes references to other data*

The comparison of the start- and end-project self-assessments shows that we have succeeded in enhancing the overall FAIR-ness of the Repository. There is, however, still room for improvement when it comes to REPOPSI’s Interoperability; we plan to continue working on securing resources to be able to express metadata in a standardised knowledge representation format (I1-01M) and provide data in a machine-understandable format (I1-02D).

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